

Learning of Indonesian Language and Literature Based on Digital Technology Artificial Intelligence

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Abstract

Technological advances affect the learning process, in the past, learning was impossible without educators and direct interaction, but distance learning is now possible, thanks to advances in technology and information, students' language learning outcomes can now be uploaded to their social media accounts. This indirectly encourages students to use social media wisely. Social media is not just a medium to expose our personal lives, it seems that there is no such thing as privacy anymore. In addition, various applications can be used to support the face-to-face learning process, however, all of that cannot replace face-to-face classes, and also because of the existence of Artificial Intelligence (AI) technology has changed various aspects of our lives, including in the field of education. One area where AI has made a major contribution to language learning and benefits is its ability to provide fast feedback and evaluation. in language learning.

Keywords: *Artificial Intelligence, Indonesian Language Learning, Digital Technology, Adaptive Learning, Educational Chatbots.*

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Introduction

Learning is a relatively permanent change in behavior or behavioral potential that occurs as a result of increasing experience or practice. Learning is the result of stimulus-response interaction. A person is said to have learned if they are able to show a change in behavior. Learning is a learning process designed by teachers to improve students' thinking skills and develop creative thinking that can improve their ability to construct new knowledge. Learning is also an effort to improve mastery of subject matter. This is of course different from the definition of learning which can be interpreted as an effort to obtain intelligence and knowledge, practice it, and change behavior and reactions caused by experience. It can be concluded that the definition of learning is the process of interaction between students and teachers and learning resources in a learning environment. Learning is a process where students learn well. According to Law Number 20 of 2003, the definition of learning according to Law

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Number 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System states that learning is a process of interaction between students, educators and learning resources in a learning environment.

Teachers must continue to work hard. They need to continue to hone their skills to become good teachers. Encourage students to become active, cooperative, and responsible learners. Chasing academic information only makes students addicted. Indonesian society is not blind to smart people because there are so many smart people in the Indonesian nation. However, the Indonesian nation needs people who are noble and have noble morals (Nadim Makarim, Minister of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia Saturday, November 30, 2019). Development Through language learning that emphasizes the function of communication and reasoning, students will be able to participate and interact well in Indonesian while still paying attention to the cooperative nature of language, politeness, sensitivity, sense of nationality, and the thoughts of the creator to do so. The above possibilities can be realized through the development of national identity as an application of language learning (Syaurdin, 2014).

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Figure 1. Epistemic Role of Artificial Intelligence in Indonesian Language and Literature Learning

In this era of rapid digital development, technology has begun to be introduced into various aspects of life, including education and daily life. According to (Muthmainnah et al., 2024), a very important advancement is the emergence of artificial intelligence (AI). AI artificial intelligence that models human intelligence in machines has become an integral part of the Industrial Revolution 4.0 (Luh Putu Ary Sri Tjahyanti, 2022). The development of artificial intelligence has brought many benefits in various fields,

including in education (Management & Brown, 2021). This phenomenon is very important because AI has the potential to change the way teachers teach and the way students acquire knowledge (Rifky, 2024). The integration and development of AI into the curriculum and education system will bring great progress, providing innovative AI-based tools and applications to educators and academic institutions (Zhang et al., 2024). (Al-Ghonmein & Al-Moghrabi, 2024) This technology helps teachers understand the learning needs of each student and provide teaching that meets those needs. For example, smart technology can help teachers understand data about their students, create a better learning environment, increase student engagement, and achieve educational goals.

The growth of the digital era has changed the way people interact, transcending geographical boundaries, and rethinking old paradigms. Education is one of the fields that will be greatly impacted by this digital transformation. An era marked by rapid networks and information flows, education has also undergone significant changes (Destari et al., 2023). In particular, Indonesian language education plays an important role in building character and linguistic values in a society that is increasingly digitally integrated (Syaurdin, 2020). However, when using it, each individual has the freedom to see technology as something that brings positive benefits or conversely as something that has a negative impact (Tchanturia & Dalakishvili, 2023). Therefore, the management of technology in teaching Indonesian must be accompanied by a deep understanding so that teaching with technology can be carried out effectively and efficiently in accordance with the needs of the current digital era (Alfitoriana Purba, 2023). Therefore, to achieve more effective and sustainable educational goals, we need to make the best use of the increasingly rapid development of technology.

Figure 2. Pedagogical Impacts of Artificial Intelligence on Indonesian Language Learning

Research on the use of artificial intelligence (AI) in education is now increasingly popular. Several research papers include an article entitled "Artificial Intelligence and Learning Analytics in Teacher Education: A Systematic Review" written by Sdenka Zobeida Salas-Pilco, Kejiang Xiao (Salas-Pilco et al., 2022), containing recent research and Xinyun Hu. This article examines the teacher selection and development system using Internet-based data analysis (LA) systems and machine learning (AI) technologies in education. The article "Educational AI chatbots for learning that integrates content and language" by Kleopatra Mageira et al. (Mageira et al., 2022) discusses the use of AI technology in educational environments and the development of chatbots to support discussion culture education. Integrated language materials in foreign languages. Furthermore, Nuria Haristiani discusses the use of chatbots as a language learning medium, discussing and We analyze the various types of chatbots

available. For learning media. On the other hand, Innocent Chiawa Igbokwe, in “The Application of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Educational Management” (Igbokwe, 2023), also discusses the advantages and disadvantages of applying AI to educational management. as a way to overcome it. ethical issues related to the application of AI in education. Finally, in “Artificial Intelligence in Education: A Review” (Chen et al, 2020), Lijia Chen, Pingping Chen, and Zhijian Lin discuss the impact of AI on education and explore how AI will affect our education trying to assess the impact it will have. Especially on the aspects of administration, teaching and learning.

This study focuses on the impact of AI digital technology on Indonesian language education. Research on the positive and negative impacts of AI on Indonesian language teaching is still rare, but in this era of Merdeka Belajar, teachers need to master innovative technology (Sain Hanafy, 2014). Therefore, teachers can use various technologies to support the teaching and learning process (Rebolledo Font de la Vall & González Araya, 2023). For example, AI can help teachers learn Indonesian more effectively (Buddha et al., 2024). For example, ChatGPT, a recently popular AI technology, can provide answers to questions asked. However, behind the convenience of AI there is another problem. Continuous use of AI can make students lazy because they are used to getting direct answers without going through the thinking process.

Research methodology

This study discusses the impact of using artificial intelligence (AI) in learning Indonesian. The research method used in this paper is a scientific method that aims to collect data according to specific goals and uses (Sugiyono, 2019). The main data sources of this study include literature related to the research topic, academic journals, and online news. The data collection process involves accessing, reading, evaluating, and recording various materials contained in these sources. The collected data is then filtered and integrated into a theoretical framework to form the basis for the discussion and conclusions of the study. The purpose of this approach is to comprehensively understand the impact of implementing AI in the context of learning Indonesian. Therefore, this study provides detailed insights into how AI digital technology can impact and improve the process of learning Indonesian.

Results and Discussion

The Effectiveness of Using AI in Improving Students' Learning Skills

The use of AI technology in Indonesian language learning has a significant impact on student understanding and participation. AI enables the implementation of interactive learning applications such as digital exercises and educational games designed to adapt the learning experience to students' individual learning styles. According to Adlawan (2023), AI can help create more engaging and interactive learning methods, thus encouraging students to participate more actively in the learning process. For example, a chatbot used to practice conversation in Indonesian provides instant feedback and significantly increases student engagement by allowing students to practice speaking in realistic contexts (Suh et al., 2022). The adaptability and personalization provided by AI allows students to learn with materials that suit their needs and learning styles, thus having a positive impact on comprehension.

AI also plays a role in customizing learning materials to be more effectively tailored to the needs and abilities of individual students (Afrita, 2023). AI algorithms analyze data from online activities, test responses, and previous grades to create an accurate learning profile for each student (Muthmainnah et al, 2024b). Research shows that this personalization improves students' Indonesian language learning outcomes. For example, AI-based language assistants can help students find references and materials that suit their needs and provide exercises tailored to their level of understanding (Chen et al, 2024). This adaptation improves students' overall understanding and learning outcomes by ensuring that the material is delivered according to each student's ability.

In addition, AI supports educational efficiency by reducing the administrative burden on teachers and allowing them to focus on deeper interactions in the classroom (Syarafudin & Ikawati, 2020). AI can manage learning materials and provide fast and objective feedback, thereby reducing the administrative burden on teachers (Haristiani, 2019). Studies show that the use of AI-based data analysis tools in Indonesian language classes can help teachers adjust teaching strategies in real-time based on student performance, making the learning process more efficient (Li & Liang, 2019). The use of AI for administrative tasks and assessments allows teachers to focus more on teaching and interaction with students. The use of AI in Indonesian language learning can also have an impact on the development of students' critical thinking skills. AI-based learning tools such as word games and chatbot-based exercises encourage students to think creatively and encourage them to think independently (Widdows et al., 2024). Through interactive games with new vocabulary and word usage, students can develop critical thinking skills (Mageira et al., 2022). However, excessive reliance on AI technology can have an impact on students' critical and independent thinking skills. Research shows that while AI can help find answers, it is important to balance its use with activities that encourage active critical thinking (Syanurdin, 2020).

However, there are also several obstacles and challenges in the use of AI. One of the biggest challenges is the risk of student dependence on technology which can reduce active participation in learning. In addition, the digital divide between students who do and do not have access to advanced technology exacerbates educational disparities. Recent research highlights the importance of ensuring equal access to technology, addressing dependence on AI, and developing strategies to ensure that this technology remains effective and beneficial (Dianne Adlawan, 2023). Addressing these challenges requires a thoughtful approach to using AI in a way that supports and enhances students' learning experiences without sacrificing active student engagement.

Benefits of Using AI for Students and Teachers in Learning Indonesian

The use of AI in Indonesian language learning provides many important benefits for students and teachers. One of the main benefits is AI's ability to create personalized and adaptive learning experiences. AI analyzes student learning data to identify weaknesses and strengths, so that teachers can adjust more effective teaching strategies. For example, a study (Ibnu Fitrianto, 2024) shows that the use of AI in language learning can increase student engagement, motivation, and learning outcomes through a more adaptive and inclusive curriculum approach. In addition, AI can also increase the efficiency of managing administrative and educational tasks. By automating mundane tasks such as assessment and reporting, teachers can focus more on more important aspects of pedagogy, such as direct interaction with students and developing well-thought-out teaching strategies. A study conducted by (Ibrahim bin Salem, 2024) found that the use of AI tools for data-driven learning analysis provides

real-time feedback to teachers, allowing them to adjust teaching methods in real-time based on student performance. This makes it more efficient and educational.

AI also plays a role in developing critical thinking skills and creativity for students. AI technologies such as chatbots and interactive learning platforms encourage students to think more critically and independently when solving problems or completing certain tasks. According to (Mageira et al., 2022), AI-based learning tools such as Words word games and interactive exercises can help students think more creatively and develop problem-solving skills. This is very important in society. The process of learning Indonesian.

AI provides more comprehensive and faster access to various learning resources and references. This technology allows us to identify learning materials that meet the needs and learning styles of our students, thereby increasing their interest and engagement in the learning process. Adlawan's study (2023) emphasized that AI facilitates the enrichment of learning materials by adjusting content to students' learning preferences, thereby increasing understanding of the material being taught.

However, despite these benefits, the use of AI in education has its challenges, including the risk of over-reliance on technology and the digital divide. These challenges can reduce student engagement and lead to disparities in access to education. Therefore, it is important for educators and policymakers to develop smart and comprehensive strategies to integrate AI into learning systems and optimize the benefits of this technology without sacrificing critical thinking skills or student autonomy. Therefore, the integration of AI in Indonesian language learning offers a variety of significant potential benefits, but requires a careful implementation approach to optimize learning outcomes and overcome potential challenges (Shuai Xu, 2023).

Conclusion

The use of AI in Indonesian language learning by students and teachers shows that AI has great potential to improve the quality of learning. AI can help personalize learning, provide faster and more accurate feedback, and enrich teaching methods. For teachers, AI can function as a supporting tool in designing more effective and efficient teaching materials. However, the application of AI also requires infrastructure preparation and increased digital literacy of teachers and students so that the use of AI can be optimal. The use of AI also opens up opportunities to develop more adaptive and personalized teaching methods, but this must be balanced with investment in teacher training and technology infrastructure. This study also highlights the importance of education policies that support the use of AI and the need for ongoing assessment to ensure a positive impact on student learning outcomes.

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